

ISic0432

Funerary stone of Iobacchus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Iobacchus

2. vixit · annisanis

3. dies

4. septe(m) IIII

Apparatus

Text of CIL. Mommsen interprets as: Iobacchus vixit anis IIII dies septe(m)

The final 's' in the CIL transcription is bigger than the other letters and slanted, perhaps representing a Latin cursive 's'.

Translation (en)

Iobacchus; he lived four years and seven days.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491660

EDCS 21900494

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7152 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0432. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335652>